

incidence in Oct, when temperatures were 20.7-32.7 °C with a mean rainfall of 18.2 mm. In general, thrips damage was high after heavy rains followed by a prolonged (40-45 d) dry spell. □

Heliothis armigera development and damage to rice

A. T. Barrion and J.A. Litsinger, IRRI

Heliothis armigera (Hübner), a highly polyphagous insect, has occasionally been reported as a rice pest. Larvae from six host plants — maize, sorghum, wheat, pigeonpea, mungbean, and tobacco — were reared on the hosts. Upon emergence, mated pairs from each host were caged in 12- × 39-cm mylar tubes with 30- and 75-d-old IR1917-3-17 rice plants. Honey solution (10%) was added in a wick receptacle.

Moths laid eggs on the rice leaves and fully exerted panicles for 5 d. Growth and development of *H. armigera* and potential damage of rice panicles by larvae were determined.

The six phenotypes of *Heliothis* laid more eggs on 75-d-old plants, with 88% of the eggs laid on grains between the lemma and palea (see table). The higher

Development and gain damage by 6 *Heliothis armigera* phenotypes^a on IR1917-3-17 rice. ^b IRRI greenhouse, Nov 1985-May 1986.

Phenotype source	Ovipositional preference ^c (no. of eggs/plant)		Egg hatch (%)	Larval wt (mg)	Growth index ^d	Adult		Damaged grains ^e (%)
	30 DAS	75 DAS				Wt (mg)	Longevity (d)	
	Pigeonpea	6 c				62 c	87 a	
Mungbean	8 c	88 b	90 a	81 c	-	-	28 b	
Tobacco	6 c	59 c	88 a	79 c	-	-	20 c	
Maize	26 a	110 a	94 a	126 a	0.3 ab	157 a	4 a	45 a
Sorghum	18 b	94 ab	86 a	119 a	0.2 b	143 b	4 a	40 a
Wheat	22 ab	103 a	92 a	102 b	0.4 a	138 b	2 b	19 c

^a *Heliothis* phenotype from tobacco was collected by Dr. K. Klaus from Pangasinan. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^c DAS = days after sowing. ^d Growth index = no. of larvae becoming pupae (%) divided by mean developmental period (d). ^e Damaged grains = no. of grains with holes/450 grains × 100 (Note: the number of grains of 5 panicles was thinned to 450).

oviposition rate in 75-d-old rice plants could have been triggered by their floral nectar production.

Egg hatch was high, 86-94%. Newly hatched larvae readily fed on young leaves and soon dispersed. Larvae that were able to locate the panicles grew; those that failed, died.

Heliothis phenotypes from legumes and tobacco developed only to the 4th instar. Phenotypes reared from graminaceous crops — maize, sorghum, and wheat — developed completely.

Rice and these crops may have similar

chemical constituents.

Development from egg to adult took 39-52 d. No additional molt (7th instar) that prolonged larval development was observed.

Host potential of rice was very low, with a 0.2-0.4 growth index, 79-126 mg larvae weight, 138-152 mg adult weight, and 24 d adult longevity.

The larval stages of all phenotypes damaged grain. In a no-choice test, larvae produced 19-45% damaged grains. The damage was similar to that made by *Conocephalus*. □

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Evaluation of weed control methods in Bhutan

P. M. Pradhan and G. B. Chettri, Centre for Agricultural Research and Development (CARD), Department of Agriculture, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan

Labor constraints can make timely weeding of rice crops difficult in Bhutan. We compared hand and rotary weeding with butachlor alone or supplemented with a single hand or rotary weeding. The trial was conducted at CARD in a split-plot design with three replications. Varieties Pusa 33 and IR36 were subplot

Effect of weed control method on rice yield. CARD, Wangdiphodrang, Bhutan, 1984.

Weed control method	Mean grain yield ^a (t/ha, 14% MC)			Weeding operation		RAVC ^e MBCR ^e (\$)	
	Pusa 33	IR36	Mean ^b	Time ^c (d/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)		
	Rotary weeding 35 DT	5.9	6.0	5.9 bcd	16		13
Rotary weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.6	5.9	5.8 cd	22	18	1196	negative
Hand weeding 35 DT	5.2	5.6	5.4 d	27	22	1102	0
Hand weeding 21 and 40 DT	5.4	6.0	5.7 cd	53	44	1153	3.3
Butachlor 2 DT	6.3	1.2	6.8 abc	2	50	1368	10.5
Butachlor 2 DT + rotary weeding 35 DT	5.8	6.8	6.3 abcd	7	55	1270	6.1
Butachlor 2 DT + hand weeding 35 DT	6.5	6.6	6.5 ab	9	56	1317	7.3
Weedy check	4.2	4.8	4.5 e	-	-	-	-
Weed-free check	6.7	7.1	6.9 a	-	-	-	-

^a MC = moisture content. ^b Separation of means by DMRT at the 5% level. ^c Includes time taken to apply butachlor. ^d Based on a labor cost of \$0.83/day. Includes cost of butachlor at \$1.22/kg formulated product (5% granules). ^e Based on a rough rice price of \$0.21/kg.